
OCCIPITO FRONTAL CIRCUMFERENCE IN THREE WEST AFRICAN POPULATIONS

Odokuma E.I

¹Dept of Anatomy, Delta State University, Abraka Nigeria. Email: secretfiles1800@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The usefulness of Occipito frontal circumference in facilitating proper identification of skeletal remains and in emphasizing a common origin of studied populations is far reaching. This study involved 699 (male 361; female 338) volunteers whose age ranged 18 years and over. Respondents were selected along three ethnic groups including Urhobo (male 156; female 147), Ibo (male 141 female 145) and Edo (male 64; female 46) by a stratified random method. The Occipito frontal circumference was measured using standard techniques. Occipito frontal circumference exhibited strong sexual dimorphism and was useful in differentiating inter and intra population groups. In spite of these findings, significant peculiarities which enabled intracultural differentiation commonly occurred as exhibited by occipito frontal circumference in this study. Inevitably therefore, craniometric studies are most essential in the study of population dynamics especially with respect to quantitative variables.

KEYWORDS; occiput, sexual-dimorphism, urhobo, anthropology, craniometry, occipito-frontal circumference.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of the cranium of either a dry skull or of a living being is of significant importance to the study and comparison of populations with various fundamental differences like racial, geographic, ethnic and dietary characteristics. This information is useful in correlating occipito frontal circumference (OFC) with other cranial measurements in studies of primate phylogeny. Medically, an analysis of occipito frontal circumference expresses another aspect of growth and development and permits critical evaluation of unusually large, small or misshapen crania (Haack and Neihoff, 1971).

Craniometric data is used in mainstream science to compare modern-day animal species, and to analyze the evolution of the human species in archeology. Fossil hominids are often found fragmented and are reconstructed upon a paradigm according to the law of correlation. Jerrison, (1979) noted the paucity of whole crania of australopithecines and habilines and remarked that cranial statistics seem to conform to foci of averages based on a few reconstructions.

Since man's brain is relatively larger than other animals, it is natural for man to conclude that the brain is the hallmark of man and the measurement of it must be the key to the understanding of his unique intellectual capacity (Douglas, 1990).

Measuring of man's potential intellectual capacity from sources other than direct observations and testing is derived from direct, indirect and inferential data. The direct data is obtained from measuring cranial capacity and examining casts which 'expose' the interior of the skull. The indirect evidence comes from the study of comparative brain sizes, which is based on the assumption that there is a correlation between brain size and configuration, and behavioral studies. Other indirect evidence comes from the study of fossil remains of non-cranial parts which infer manual dexterity and visual acuity (Douglas, 1990).

Attempts at explaining homogeneity of African populations have led to a number of studies. Howells, (1989); Froment, (1992a) and Lahr, (1996) suggested that despite the general opinion that Africans did appear to be homogenous in certain morphologic characteristics, observed polymorphisms were far from homogenous. In another study, Hiernaux (1976) explained that the variations of craniometric characteristics were distinctly different from the previous racial categorizations of Africans (Leaky, 1935; Coon, 1971). Through skull morphology, population differentiation has been explored previously by three main recent studies (Hiernaux 1976; Howells 1989; Froment, 1992; 1998), showing that not only vault features but also various facial characteristics are responsible for both inter and intra-regional differences within sub-Saharan Africa. Hiernaux, (1966, 1968, 1974, 1976), highlighted on inter- and intra-population variability in sub-Saharan Africa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The sample population for this study included 699 (male 361, female 338) whose age ranged from between 18 years and over. Data was obtained from persons whose parents and grand parents were of Nigerian origin and showed no obvious physical defect. Respondents were selected along three culture lines; Urhobo (male 156; female 147), Ibo (male 141 female 145) and Edo (male 64; female 46) speaking people by a random stratified method.

Sexual variation had previously been shown to affect gross cranial patterns hence the data was separated along gender lines. All selected individuals were all apparently able bodied volunteers whose parents and grand parents were pure breeds of the three cultures assessed. Any subject that was not able bodied or who had any obvious physical deformity affecting statues was excluded from the study. Data from closely related individuals were excluded to avoid familiar peculiarities that may occur with such measurements.

Consent was obtained from each respondent or their legal guardians and it conformed with the provisions of the Declaration of Helsinki in 1995 (as revised in Edinburgh 2000), Tyebkahan (2003).

Measurements were taken using a steel tape over the occiput and frontal bone and means, standard deviation and range of the results were determined (Table 2). Comparisons between the three tribes were conducted by multiple analyses of variance and presented in Table 1.

RESULTS AND ANALYSES

As shown in Table 1, sex had a significant effect on OFC (Table 1). This effect was a result of the differences observed between the Urhobo and Ibo males and their female respectively.

The mean OFC for Edo people was $55.69\text{cm} \pm 2.82\text{ cm}$ as shown in Table 1. Range was $51.4\text{cm} - 69.2\text{cm}$ (Table 2). There was a significant difference between male and female OFC values within the Edo group (Table 1).

The mean occipito-frontal circumference for the Ibo speaking tribe was $55.19\text{cm} \pm 2.31\text{cm}$ (Table 2). Maximum length was 62.10cm and minimum length was 49.00 cm as shown in Table 2. There was an observed significant difference between male and the female values (Table 1).

The mean OFC for the measured Urhobo population was $55.39\text{cm} \pm 3.06\text{ cm}$ (Table 2). Minimum value was 17.72 and maximum value 65.10 (Table 2). The results for Ibo and Edo tribes are also shown.

DISCUSSION

The mean Occipito Frontal Circumference for the studied populations was 55.35cm with STD of 2.74 cm and minimum value of 17.72cm and maximum value of 69.20cm . Generally, tribe had a significant effect on OFC, $p < 0.05$. The effect of gender on OFC was also significant $p < 0.05$ therefore this parameter exhibited marked sexual dimorphism and showed strong cultural similarities and thus it may be useful perhaps in defining intercultural groups.

CONCLUSIONS

The Occipito Frontal Circumference of three indigenous West African cultures has been presented highlighting certain features common to West African and perhaps indeed African populations. It has also been shown that craniometric patterns are significant indices for differentiation of population groups and cultures. In spite of these observations, differences which enable intracultural differentiation occur as exhibited by craniometric patterns in this study. Inevitably therefore, craniometric studies are most essential in the study of population dynamics especially with respect to quantitative variables as shown in this study. More importantly, the benefits of this study in forensic medicine are far reaching. Finally, this study has further demonstrated that the three studied populations may have evolved from a common ancestral origin.

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Table 1: Distribution of occipito frontal circumference in three Nigerian ethnic groups			
Ethnic group	Sex		LSD
	Female	Male	
Edo	56.24 _a ¹	55.30 _b ¹	0.34
Ibo	55.95 _a ²	54.43 _b ¹	0.21
Urhobo	55.34 _a ²	55.45 _a ¹	0.21
SEM	0.18	0.13	

Means with different superscript, '1' or '2', along the columns and subscript, 'a' or 'b', along the rows, are significantly different (p < 0.05).

Table 2; Mean, standard deviation and range of parameters of the three ethnic groups

Tribe	Variable	Mean	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
Urhobo	OFC	55.35	2.74	17.72	69.20
Ibo	OFC	55.18	2.31	49.00	62.10
Edo	OFC	55.69	2.81	51.40	69.20

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